

Auxiliary Propulsion Based on Wave Energy Converters

Nick Markov¹, Grigor Nikolov¹, Silvia Kirilova¹, Rumen Kishev¹

¹Bulgarian Ship Hydrodynamics Centre, Institute of Metal Science, Equipment and Technologies
with Hydro- and Aerodynamics Centre “Acad. Angel Balevski”, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Varna, Bulgaria.

ABSTRACT

This study presents a proof of concept for new auxiliary propulsion. The proposed design includes open to the sea ship compartments. Seawater oscillates inside the specially shaped compartments due to the relative ship motions in waves. The curved profile of these compartments deflects the water backwards from its natural vertical flow, and the water inertia pushes the vessel forward. The new wave energy converter does not have any parts that move or protrude outside the hull. The converter can operate entirely underwater, but CFD and model tests show that efficiency increases when it crosses the water surface. In the latter case, different water levels inside and outside the compartment act as a non-return valve that enhances the flow in the backward direction. The new auxiliary propulsion can produce thrust comparable to the added resistance of a ship in waves. It can reduce the carbon footprint of marine vessels and increase the operability range of battery-powered ships

KEY WORDS: Energy-saving devices, auxiliary propulsion, wave energy converters, WEC, wave-powered ships

INTRODUCTION

The International Maritime Organization has set ambitious new targets for marine transportation to curb climate change. The current ship powering technology, however, does not provide a single general solution to meet these targets. Therefore, the strategy under consideration is complex. One of its aspects relies on energy-saving methods, such as design speed reduction, hull resistance reduction, increase in propulsion efficiency, and utilization of wind and wave energy. This study presents a new environmentally friendly method for a direct transformation of wave energy to ship forward motion. The objective is to improve the ship Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) by reducing the need for additional engine power in rough weather conditions. The ambition is to develop a wave energy drive (WE-Drive) that counteracts the added resistance in waves more efficiently than the bulbous bows suppress wave resistance in calm water. The constraint is that the efficiency gain should significantly outweigh the loss in displacement.

Wave energy converters (WEC) have been in use for years. Several converter types produce electricity from wave energy (Czech and Bauer, 2012). Some of these WEC are also studied for ship propulsion applications (Wu et al., 2018). Their efficiency, however, suffers losses due to the double conversion of wave motions to electricity and back to forward motion.

Other devices convert wave energy directly to ship forward motion. Usually, they include parts that move and protrude outside the hull (Isshiki and Murakami 1986; Bockmann and Steen 2016; Moreira et al., 2020). Such devices, however, add complexity to design, manufacturing and maintenance.

The concept presented here describes a new wave energy conversion that transfers the kinetic energy of the ship's relative motions directly into forward motion. The converter does not include any moving or protruding parts. The method's efficiency relies on the significant inertia of the ship motions in waves.

The authors of this study developed the novel concept, evaluated it with two different numerical methods, and validated the numerical results with model tests of an isolated WE-Drive device.

DESCRIPTION OF THE CONVERTER

The converter utilizes the seawater motion in single or multiple internal hull compartments. The compartments are open to the sea and have curved walls that deflect the vertical inertial water flow backwards. The water inertia creates non-zero average horizontal reaction forces on the inner compartment walls, similar to the resultant force produced by flow acting in a pipe bend (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Examples of wave energy converter shapes and locations (not to scale)

The specialized compartments can be designed as a double-walled bow structure, a tank between twin propellers, or port and starboard roll dampeners. The curved compartments are open at both ends. Their upper openings can be designed to be always underwater. Alternatively, the upper openings can be designed to cross the water surface while the ship moves in waves. In the latter case, the compartment can transiently elevate water above the external water level when the bow moves up (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The differential between the two water levels acts as a non-return valve, increasing the efficiency of the energy conversion (not to scale)

The elevated water and its drainage rate depend on the area ratio between the upper and lower compartment openings and the compartment length. The weight of the elevated water acts as a non-return valve enhancing the water egress through the bottom opening while the compartment is moving with acceleration pointing downwards. We will demonstrate that this phenomenon improves the efficiency of the wave energy converter and generates greater propulsive forces.

Both surface-crossing and underwater compartment types may require side hull openings at their upper ends. The surface-crossing compartment side openings, if needed, would be located above the mean water line, so they would not affect the calm water resistance. A surface-crossing compartment may also require vertical wall separators if the elevated water amount is large enough to affect ship stability.

EVALUATION OF THE CONVERTER

The converter location, volume and dimensions were carefully considered because the conversion efficiency was expected to increase for higher flow rates through the curved compartment. The ship bow location will be selected for this study because the vertical accelerations near the ship bow can be significant. Also, the bow design can be easier to modify because the bow area is relatively free of equipment. The flow rate and the amount of water transiently elevated above the waterline (Fig. 2) should depend on the ratio between the upper and lower openings and the length of the compartment.

The area-ratio assumption was verified by evaluating the performance of two simplified horn-shaped compartments (Fig. 3). Here, Horn #1 has a larger area ratio between the upper and lower openings than Horn #2. Both horns are short in length.

The flow through the horns was simulated using the meshless Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method, a Navier-Stokes solver (Ansys Fluent), and forced-oscillation experiments in a model basin.

Relative ship motions were initially simulated by performing vertical forced-oscillations in calm water for Horn #1 using the open-source DualSPHysics software (Domínguez et al., 2021). 2D simulations were performed with 830,000 multi-phase particles and 3D simulations with 6,800,000 single-phase particles. Particle distances were set to $dp = 0.004$ m. Verlet step algorithm, default time step and artificial viscosity treatment were selected. The SPH simulations confirmed that water surface crossing could produce a non-return valve effect. Fig. 4 demonstrates vertical oscillations of Horn #1 conducted entirely underwater. As expected, the horizontal flow through the bottom horn opening has different directions (the black arrows) depending on the direction of the vertical horn acceleration (the white arrows).

Fig 3. Two horn-shaped compartments used in this study (dimensions in meters)

Fig. 4. Vertical underwater horn oscillations produce bi-directional flow at the bottom horn opening

The patterns change (Fig. 5) when the horn is allowed to cross the water surface. In this case, the horizontal flow direction is predominantly to the right irrespectively of the vertical acceleration. The “non-return valve” effect enhances the exit flow and balances the inertial and pressure force components in the upper trajectory range, as will be discussed in detail later. Variation of dp ($\pm 25\%$) did not change the character of the presented velocity patterns.

Fig. 5. Vertical surface-crossing oscillations bias the flow direction at the bottom opening (the non-return valve effect)

Physical tests in a model basin were conducted based on the numerical simulations. The test setup is shown in Fig 6. The tests included vertical forced oscillations in two regimes (Fig. 7). Force and motion measurements for Horn #1 were conducted using a 6-axis load cell (AMTI MC3A, 2% accuracy) and a 1-DOF linear transducer position sensor (type PT1A, 1% accuracy). The sampling rate of the NI DAQ was set to 100 Hz. The total estimated uncertainty of $\pm 2.3\%$ is adequate to support the conclusions of this presentation. The measured motion parameters were fed as input in the following simulations.

Fig. 6. Model test setup with a 6-axis load cell and a 1-DOF vertical motion measurement

The first test results did not show significant average values for the horizontal force. To better understand the test findings, several forced-oscillation tests (in calm water and zero current) were simulated in Ansys Fluent using the 3D Volume-of-Fluid method with 5,300,000 elements (Figs. 8-9), DES k-omega SST model and DEFINE_CG_MOTION solver.

Fig. 7. The two motion ranges used during the surface-crossing and underwater tests

Fig. 8. Ansys Fluent 3D dynamic layering mesh, where the top and bottom of the domain are static boundaries, while all others move using the measured motion parameters from the tests

Fluent offered some advantages over the SPH 3D simulations. The forces acting on the internal and the external horn walls were outputted separately. Also, the SPH pressure integration along the horn walls was rather noisy, affecting the force averages. While the grid convergence presented at the end of the section shows that the simulated with Fluent mean forces are reliable.

Fig. 9. A close-up view near the converter (Fluent, high-quality pure hexahedra unstructured blocked ICEM CFD mesh, $y+ \approx 1$)

Fig. 10. Measured data from an underwater forced-oscillation test in the model scale

Table 1. Statistics from the underwater forced-oscillation test

Test: Data_11		Avg. T	Avg. ω	Avg ampl. a	Avg ampl. a	
Interval: 2 s -20 s		[s]	[rad/s]	[m/s^2]	[g]	
		0.97	6.5	4.7	0.48	
Channel	Units	Mean	Max	Min	StDev	Avg P-P
Z	m	-0.01	0.11	-0.13	0.08	0.22
F _x	N	-3.19	11.77	-23.25	8.37	20.16
F _z	N	8.27	80.63	-40.46	37.81	106.46

Based on the new CFD analysis, the horn shape was modified to increase the internal flow rate. Another test model (Horn #2) was manufactured with a larger lower opening (Fig. 6).

The tests with Horn #2 showed consistent and significant non-zero average horizontal forces. Sample time series and statistic for the relevant data channels are given in Fig. 10 and Table 1. Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 show the agreement between the predicted and measured forces. Note that the measurements include the total forces acting on the internal and external horn walls.

Fig. 11. Correlation between measurements and a Fluent simulation for an underwater test

Fig. 12. Correlation between measurements and Fluent for a test with water surface crossing

The CFD analysis revealed further detail - the average forces on the internal and external walls have opposite signs. Fig. 13 compares the external and internal horizontal forces acting on Horn # 2 while oscillating underwater.

The force averages shift further apart for oscillations crossing the water surface (Fig 14). Note that the converter-generated thrust would be significantly higher in comparison to the test-measured total thrust because only the internal average forces have a practical use for generating auxiliary propulsion (Fig. 15).

Fig. 13. Fluent simulation showing the horizontal force components have opposite sign averages on the external and internal walls of Horn #2

Fig. 14. Fluent simulation showing the opposite sign averages on the external and internal walls shift further apart when Horn #2 oscillates through the water surface

Fig. 15. Fluent simulation comparing the horizontal force component acting on the internal wall for underwater and surface-crossing oscillations of Horn #2

Finally, to quantify the new auxiliary thrust, the Horn #2 performance was evaluated with a realistic relative motions scenario. An existing ship model was selected, with model-scale dimensions so that the volume of

Horn #2 represents 3% of the ship displacement. Relative motions of this ship model (Fig. 16) had been previously simulated with a potential-flow solver (ShipMo) and had been correlated with model tests. Fig. 16 also includes the added resistance of the ship, which was calculated for head waves using Gerritsma and Beukelman's method.

Fig. 16. The three data points selected for CFD simulations

To approximately estimate the Horn #2 efficiency, a single wave-energy converter was assumed to be located at the bow, where the relative motions have large amplitudes. Fluent CFD forced-oscillation simulations in calm water were conducted for Horn #2 using the amplitudes and periods of the ship relative motions in three regular head waves encountered at 75% of the ship design speed. The three input points are shown with square markers (Fig. 16). Note that the ship hull was not modeled in Fluent.

The added resistance in Fig. 16 is presented in the non-dimensional form $R_{AW} = R / (\rho g \zeta_a^2 B^2 / L_{pp})$. The relative motion at the bow is divided by the regular wave amplitude $Z_R = Z / \zeta_a$; λ is the wavelength; L_{pp} is the ship length between the perpendiculars; B is the maximum breadth of the waterline, ρ is the water density; g is the gravitational acceleration.

Four cases were analyzed with Fluent (Table 2). Two of them, with and without current, use the same wave period. The simulation with current modeled the effect of the ship forward motion. The inlet and outlet boundary conditions (Fig. 8) included 5% turbulent intensity. The hydraulic diameter was set equal to the bottom horn diameter. Two more cases simulate two different wave periods without current. Horn #2 was crossing the water surface in all these simulations.

An average ratio of 32% was calculated (Table 2) between the auxiliary thrust predicted in Fluent and the main propulsion thrust measured in-house for the original hull (self-propulsion model tests in calm water, which had been previously conducted according to the ITTC standards in a 200m x 16m x 6.5m towing tank; < 1% error). An average ratio of 104% was predicted between the auxiliary thrust (Fluent) and the added resistance in waves for the original hull calculated by Gerritsma and Beukelman's method. As theorized, this type of wave energy conversion can efficiently counteract the added resistance since the relative ship motions drive both the added resistance in waves and the evaluated here auxiliary thrust.

The CFD also shows a horizontal force increase for horn oscillations with current (Table 2). The predicted higher average thrust in this case could result from a pressure drop induced by the current velocities. The lower pressure helps the exit flow at the bottom opening when the horn is at the lowest end of its trajectory. This phenomenon will be discussed in the next section.

Table 2. The auxiliary propulsion thrust AP compared to the main propulsion thrust P and the added resistance R_{AW}

*The only simulation with current (= 75% design speed)			
λ/L_{PP}	Z_R	AP/P	AP/R_{AW}
0.95	1.73	18%	130%
1.40	2.84	34%	82%
1.40*	2.84	52%	126%
1.90	2.12	26%	80%
Steepness: 1/40	Average:	32%	104%

Grid convergence test was performed for $\lambda/L_{PP}=1.4$ (Table 2). The difference in the average predicted auxiliary thrust was just 0.09% between the coarsest and the densest grids (Fig. 17).

The forced-oscillation approach presented in this section presumes an insignificant change in the heave and pitch relative motions due to the presence of a relatively small (compared to the ship displacement) horn-shaped compartment near the bow.

DISCUSSION

The presented wave energy converter relies on water flowing through curved compartments. The relative vertical ship motions create inertial force perpendicular to the upper horn opening and nearly zero inertial force perpendicular to the bottom horn opening. The hydrodynamic pressure also varies at both openings. The inertial force and the pressure differential work together to create seawater flow through the horn. According to momentum conservation law, the mass flow (Fig. 1) produces a unidirectional horizontal force component:

$$F_x^{(1)}(t) = \rho A v(t)^2 \quad (1)$$

where A and $v(t)$ are the area and horizontal fluid velocity at the bottom horn opening, and ρ is the water density. However, the underwater oscillations result in sign-changing horizontal forces, albeit with non-zero averages (Fig. 14). The non-zero average forces suggest that the pipe-bend effect is present as expected, while the changing force direction implies additional dynamics at play. The additional dynamics is attributed to the hydrodynamic pressure at the bottom opening that creates a second variable force component:

$$F_x^{(2)}(t) = A \Delta p(t) \quad (2)$$

where A is the area and $\Delta p(t)$ is the hydrodynamic pressure at the bottom horn opening. Both formulas apply only to 90 degree bends. For different bend angles, the upper opening would also contribute to the horizontal force.

The positive peaks of the force (Fig. 15) imply that the hydrodynamic pressure component $F_x^{(2)}$ produces suction at the upper trajectory end, which overwhelms the unidirectional inertial component $F_x^{(1)}$ that always points forward. The elevated water weight in the crossing-surface case can increase the converter efficiency by enhancing the downflow.

The above assumption was validated with 3D DualSPHysics simulations. The color map for the velocity magnitude shows that a low-pressure area forms near the bottom horn opening, while the horn is decelerating on its way up (Fig. 18).

Fig.17. The three grids used for the convergence test

The low pressure is caused by a vortex shedding from the bottom horn wall. The suction at the bottom opening balances the inertial forces and the inner flow velocity becomes zero. The zero flow velocity also zeroes the inertial force component $F_x^{(1)}$, while the suction at the bottom opening produces a force component $F_x^{(2)}$ that opposes the thrust. At this point, the resultant horizontal force crosses the x-axis and becomes positive (Fig. 15). The surface crossing helps in this case because it prolongs the duration of the exit flow, shortening the time when the inertial force component is insignificant and when the suction prevails. The vortex shedding and the hydrodynamic pressure may be somewhat different if the horn is integrated into a ship hull and opens at the flat ship keel. Therefore, the new wave-energy converter needs to be evaluated further, which will be the focus of our next study.

Fig. 18. DualSPHysics 3D simulation showing a low-pressure vortex shedding from the horn bottom and moving up, while the horn is decelerating on its way up

Another point of interest lies at the lower end of the horn trajectory. The forward ship speed creates a flow that reduces the pressures at the keel level. This flow counteracts the hydrostatic pressure and enhances the water egress. The increased exit flow also increases the force component $F_x^{(1)}$, which results in lower force troughs (Fig. 19).

The discussion has been focused on the average forces. Ship speed oscillates in wave conditions due to the variable wave-induced loads on the hull. The CFD results show that the converter-generated thrust peaks near the trajectory troughs (Fig. 15). The next study with a ship model would verify whether this translates into a reduction of the speed dynamics for a bow located converter. The next study will also evaluate a converter located at the stern where the external hull curvature may be opposite to the horn curvature, and where an inverted upside-down horn may improve both the speed dynamics and the average speed.

Fig.19. Fluent simulation for Horn #2 oscillations with and without current

Converters installed at the port and starboard side of the ship will be studied to evaluate how they may affect roll damping. A portion of the roll energy would be converted into forward motion in this configuration. The motion reduction is expected to be more noticeable than for converters located at the bow or the stern due to the significant difference in the transverse and longitudinal metacentric heights.

CONCLUSIONS

Computer simulations and model tests show that seawater flow through curved hull compartments can convert relative motions into horizontal forces with non-zero average values. The converter efficiency increases when the compartment upper opening crosses the water surface. The efficiency also increases if the compartment oscillates in a current simulating the ship forward speed.

The presented wave energy converter can produce propulsive forces comparable in magnitude to the added resistance in waves. Implemented as auxiliary propulsion, it can reduce the carbon footprint of marine vessels and extend the operability range of battery-powered ships.

The next step would be to evaluate the auxiliary propulsion with realistically shaped compartments integrated into a ship model.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was partially supported by the Bulgarian Ministry of Education and Science under the National Research Program "Young scientists and postdoctoral students" approved by DCM # 577 / 17.08.2018.

REFERENCES

- Böckmann, E, Steen, S. (2016). "Model test and simulation of a ship with wavefoils", *Applied Ocean Research*, Volume 57, 8-18, ISSN 0141-1187, doi.org/10.1016/j.apor.2016.02.002.
- Czech, B., Bauer, P., (2012). "Wave Energy Converter Concepts: Design Challenges and Classification," *IEEE Industrial Electronics Magazine*, vol. 6, no. 2, 4-16.
- Dominguez, J.M., Fourtakas, G., Altomare, C., Canelas, R.B., Tafuni, A., Garcia-Feal, O., Martínez-Estévez, I., Mokos, A., Vacondio, R., Crespo, A.J.C., Roger,s B.D., Stansby, P.K., Gómez-Gesteira, M. (2021) "DualSPHysics: from fluid dynamics to multiphysics problems." *Computational Particle Mechanics*, doi:10.1007/s40571-021-00404-2.
- Gerritsma, J., Beukelman, W. (1972) "Analysis of the resistance increase in waves of a fast cargoship", *International Shipbuilding Progress*, Vol.19, 285-293.
- Isshiki, H, Murakami, M. (1986) "Wave power utilization into ship propulsion", *Proceedings of the FifihInternational Symposium on Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering*, Tokyo, Vol. 2, 580.
- Moreira, D., Mathias, N., Morais, T., (2020). "Dual flapping foil system for propulsion and harnessing wave energy: A 2D parametric study for unaligned foil configurations", *Ocean Engineering*, 215.
- Wu, B., Chen, T., Jiang, J., Li, G., Zhang, Y., Ye, Y. (2018). "Economic assessment of wave power boat based on the performance of "Mighty Whale" and BBDB", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, , Elsevier, vol. 81(P1), 946-953.